

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SYK

(Spleen Associated Tyrosine Kinase)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	6850 / P43405 /
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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Biophysical assays: Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR), Differential Scanning Fluorimetry (DSF), Isothermal Titration Calorimetry (ITC), Bio-Layer Interferometry (BLI), Thermal Shift Assay (TSA)

Screening: SYK-FCER1G PPI TR-FRET assay for HTS

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected?

This target is a close neighbor of a target that was identified through a protein quantitative trait locus (pQTL) analysis. To expand this initial gene list, gene co-expression across all omics datasets was calculated to each list member and results were averaged across datasets. This gene was above 1.5 standard deviations (~ upper 7th percentile) of all gene's average coexpression to a target gene in the pQTL gene list.

TREAT-AD Overall Score: 3.84 (rank #701)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Overall Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Overall Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. The Center has also ranked the recency of a target's association with AD in published literature. The Literature Recency Score is on a scale of 0 to 2, with 2 being all papers linking a target and AD have been published in the most recent 5 year period. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v33.

The TREAT-AD Overall score for this target is 3.84 out of 5 (rank #701). The individual score components include 1.86 of 3 for genetics, and 1.98 out of 2 for genomics. The literature recency score is 1.74 out of 2. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SYK, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. SYK is annotated to GO terms primarily from the Autophagy, Immune Response, and Oxidative Stress biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Allen Brain Institute. The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins, points indicating the expression of the target in specific subtypes within each broad class including a label for the

highest expressing cell type for each broad class. These data indicate that SYK is expressed in microglia in healthy adult brains.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Spleen tyrosine kinase (SYK) is a cytosolic tyrosine kinase that is activated upon binding to a phosphorylated immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motif (p-ITAM) on FCER1G (1, 2). FCER1G is the common gamma subunit of the FcεRI, FcγRI and FcγRIIIa receptor complexes (3). SYK and FCER1G are nominated gene targets by the Accelerating Medicines Partnership in AD (AMP-AD) Consortium with implicated roles in AD pathology. While FCER1G was nominated based on RNAseq data, SYK was nominated based both on genetics and RNAseq data (<https://agora.adknowledgeportal.org/genes>). SYK is significantly upregulated at RNA levels in the parahippocampal region of AD patient brains. This TEP targets the interaction between the tandem SH2 domains of SYK and the p-ITAM on FCER1G, to test the hypothesis that inhibition of this interaction reduces aspects of AD pathology. Herein, we have purified SYK protein and established a biochemical assay for FCER1G binding. Crystallography of the targets and biophysical assays have also been established. High-throughput screening identified several compounds that inhibited the SYK-FCER1G interaction.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

SYK is reported to have a role in several aspects of Alzheimer's pathology. Increased levels of phosphorylated SYK are found in microglia, neurons near amyloid β (Aβ) plaques, post-mortem human AD patient brains, and models of tauopathy and AD in mice (11-13). Hyperactivated SYK increases phosphorylated-tau (p-tau), Aβ accumulation, neuroinflammation, gliosis, and reduces lysosomal tau degradation via activation of NF-κB and mTOR signaling pathways (11, 13, 14). SYK also blocks autophagic tau degradation both in vitro and in vivo (12). SYK and its binding partner FCER1G are present in microglia and macrophages in the brain and FCER1G is involved in microglial activation and phagocytosis (9, 10).

SYK is activated through binding the p-ITAM of receptor complexes. Clustering of either FcεRI, FcγRI and FcγRIIIa receptor complexes, through binding IgE/IgG, triggers the phosphorylation of the intracellular ITAM sequence of the common FCER1G subunit by either LynB or Fyn kinases. Binding of the tandem SH2 (tSH2) domains of SYK to the p-ITAM causes a LynB-mediated phosphorylation of a loop between the tSH2 and kinase domains (Fig. 1) (4, 5). Phosphorylation of the interdomain region liberates the kinase domain, which is otherwise in an autoinhibited state, allowing auto phosphorylation and activation (2, 6). SYK can also be activated via binding to the p-ITAM sequence of DAP12, which is associated with TREM2 receptor signalling (7). TREM2 has been identified as a genetic risk gene through genome wide association studies (GWAS) to have a role in impaired microglial function and neuroinflammation and is well studied in relation to AD (8).

Potent and selective ATP-competitive inhibitors of SYK have been developed and a number are in clinical trials for the treatment of various cancers, and Fostamatinib was approved by the FDA for treatment of an immune system disease chronic immune thrombocytopenia (15, 16). There are limited reports of compounds that bind to SYK-tSH2 and binding is via covalent modification of cysteines, which has the

potential to be a liability due to promiscuity (17). We sought to target the specific interaction of SYK-tSH2 and the p-ITAM sequence of FCER1G gene.

Figure 1. IgG or IgE activation of FcR (such as FcεRI, FcγRI and FcγRIIIa) induces phosphorylation of the FCER1G ITAM. SYK binds to phospho-ITAM via the tSH2 domain. Activation of SYK by phosphorylation can also occur via autophosphorylation and phosphorylation via LynB. SYK activation releases the kinase domain from an autoinhibited state and leads to activation of downstream signaling pathways (3).

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

YCharOS (<https://ycharos.com/>) is an open science organisation which has industrialised a knockout based antibody characterization platform formalised at the Montreal Neurological Institute (18) with the mission to characterize antibodies against the human proteome. YCharOS has created an open scientific ecosystem in which antibody manufacturers and knockout cell line suppliers contribute reagents to support the YCharOS' goal.

YCharOS has identified the THP-1 cell line background with adequate SYK protein expression and has developed, in collaboration with Abcam, a THP-1 knockout line. This SYK knockout line was used to characterize SYK antibodies. YCharOS' partners contributed 13 SYK antibodies which were tested side-by-side by immunoblot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. Renewable antibodies were found to be specific for one or more applications. The antibody characterization report generated by YCharOS is available on Zenodo. Complete report: [SYK antibody characterization report](#)

Protein constructs and expression methods: proteins purified

1. SYKA-c020 tagged: Human SYK tandem SH2 domains (SYK-tSH2), M6-N269. Contains an N-terminal His6 and TEV cleavage site. Protein produced in bacterial cells. Used in activity assays.
2. SYKA-c020 cleaved: Human SYK tandem SH2 domains, M6-N269. His tag removed. Protein produced in bacterial cells. Used for crystallography.
3. SYKA-c022 cleaved and biotinylated: Human SYK tandem SH2 domains, M6-N269. His tag removed. Protein produced in bacterial cells. Used in biophysical assays.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

See **Additional information (section 2)** with a list of peptides used for crystallography and assay experiments.

Figure 2. Gel filtration fractions of purified proteins.

Crystal Structures

1. SYK-tSH2 apo (PDB: [7Q63](#))
2. SYK-tSH2 in complex with the ITAM of FCER1G (PDB: [7Q5T](#))
3. SYK-tSH2 in complex with the ITAM of TYROBP (PDB: [7Q5W](#))
4. SYK-tSH2 in complex with the ITAM of CD3G (PDB: [7Q5U](#))

See **Additional information (section 3)** with details of crystallography.

A protein construct comprising the tandem SH2 domains of SYK (SYK-tSH2) was crystallized alone, or in complex with a diphospho-peptide that contains the ITAM sequence of FCER1G, the common gamma subunit of the FcεRI, FcγRI and FcγRIIIa receptor complexes. Additional structures were obtained of SYK-tSH2 with the phospho-ITAM sequence of the TYROBP (DAP12) subunit of the TREM2 receptor and the CD3G gamma subunit of the T cell receptor complex. While a structure of SYK-SH2 in complex with a phospho-ITAM (from the CD3E subunit of the TCR complex) has previously been reported (19), the co-crystal structures with FCER1G, TYROBP and CD3G phospho-ITAMs are novel.

Figure 3. Apo structure of SYK-tSH2 depicting C- and N-terminal SH2 domains (1.9 Å; PDB: 7Q63).

Apo SYK-tSH2 structure

We have obtained a crystal system to routinely produce high resolution structures (1.9 Å) of SYK-tSH2 (Fig. 3). In the apo structure, the N- and C-terminal SH2 domains of SYK (SH2-N and SH2-C, respectively), which are separated by a central linker region, are found in close contact with each other. The ITAM binding interface (not shown) is largely accessible for soaking of compounds into the crystal lattice. Previously reported structures of SYK-tSH2 in the absence of bound ligands were reported either in context of the full length protein (20) or were of poor resolution (21).

SYK-tSH2 structure in complex with FCER1G phospho-ITAM

The crystal structure of SYK-tSH2 in complex with the di-phospho-ITAM of FCER1G was solved to 2.2 Å. The asymmetric unit of the crystal form has 6 copies of both SYK-tSH2 and phospho-ITAM, giving us 6 independent “snapshots” of the complex structure. The only other reported SYK-tSH2 structure in complex with an ITAM is that of CD3E, which was solved at 3.0 Å (19). Our higher resolution structure gives us the best view to date on the nature of SYK interaction with ITAM motifs.

The FCER1G phospho-ITAM stretches across both SH2-C and SH2-N, with an average total buried surface area of 1167 Å². The N-terminal conserved ITAM “pYXXL” motif of FCER1G binds to SH2-C, while the C-terminal ITAM motif binds to SH2-N (Fig. 4A, B). The phospho-tyrosines from each ITAM motif are buried within basic pockets, while the leucines bind within adjacent hydrophobic pockets (Fig. 4B). The FCER1G N-terminal phosphotyrosine (pY65) forms a salt bridge between the phosphate group and arginine residues that reside solely within the SH2-C. In contrast, the C-terminal phosphotyrosine (pY75) binds within a pocket that is formed by both SH2 domains, making salt bridges with K232 from SH2-C, as well as arginines within SH2-N (Fig. 4C).

Two different modes of SYK/FCER1G phospho-ITAM interactions were observed, represented by 3 complexes each within the asymmetric unit of the solved crystal form. Although the mode of phospho-tyrosine and leucine interactions were similar, there were distinctly different paths of the inter-ITAM motif chains across the surface of SYK (Fig.4A). Strikingly, in one conformation only, the sidechain of R45 within SH2-N engages with pY76 from the C-terminal FCER1G ITAM motif.

Figure 4. Co-crystal structure of SYK-tSH2 with FCER1G phospho-ITAM (PDB: 7Q5T). (A) Space-filling model of SYK-tSH2 bound to a ribbon model FCER1G phospho-ITAM, showing two binding modes of the phospho-ITAM. Side chains of conserved ITAM residues are shown. (B) Alignment of ITAM motifs in receptors known to bind to SYK. (C) Close-up view of electrostatic surface features of SH2-C and -N domains in contact with conserved ITAM residues. (D) Engagement of FCER1G pY66 and pY76 with basic sidechains within the C- and N-terminal SH2 domains, respectively. SYK-R45 engages with FCER1G-pY76 in binding mode 2 only.

SYK-tSH2 structure in complex with phospho-ITAMs of TYROBP and CD3E

Additional structures of SYK-tSH2 complexed with other phospho-ITAMs were obtained, in order to explore avenues of potential selectivity of compounds that inhibit FCER1G binding to SYK. The co-crystal structure of SYK-tSH2 in complex with the phospho-ITAM of TYROBP and CD3G were solved to 2.2 and 2.4 Å, respectively (Fig. 5). Just like with the crystals of SYK-tSH2 bound to FCER1G phospho-ITAM, TYROBP and CD3G-bound crystals have 6 complexes in the unit cell. The mode of phospho-tyrosine binding in all ITAM-bound structures is very similar (Fig. 5). Unlike with the FCER1G phospho-ITAM bound structure, all 6 protein/peptide complexes of TYROBP and CD3E show a single conformation that most closely resembles FCER1G mode 2. Differences do exist in the nature of ITAM sidechain interactions and SYK-tSH2 within the inter-ITAM motifs, which is not surprising due to their limited conservation (see Fig. 4B). This may provide some scope for identifying compounds that selectively interfere with FCER1G ITAM binding to SYK.

Figure 5. Overlay of co-crystal structures of SYK-tSH2 with phospho-ITAMs of FCER1G (PDB: 7Q5T), TYROBP (PDB: 7Q5W) and CD3G (PDB: 7Q5U). SYK-tSH2 is represented as a space-filling model, while phospho-ITAMs are shown as ribbon models. Sidechains of conserved ITAM residues are also shown.

Phospho-ITAMs:
 FCER1G Mode 1
 FCER1G Mode 2
 TYROBP
 CD3G

Biochemical assay

Time Resolved Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer (TR-FRET)

A TR-FRET-based assay was established to measure binding of FCER1G phospho-ITAM to SYK-tSH2 (Fig. 6A). His-tagged SYK-tSH2 becomes bound by an anti-His antibody conjugated with a terbium donor fluorophore. Upon binding of the FITC-labelled FCER1G phospho-ITAM peptide to the 6His-SYK-tSH2/Tb-Ab complex a TR-FRET signal is produced between the donor Tb acceptor and FITC acceptor fluorophore. This signal could be titrated with increasing concentration of unlabelled FCER1G-phospho-ITAM peptide (Fig. 6B), but not with non-phosphorylated FCER1G ITAM peptide.

Figure 6. Biochemical assay for FCER1G phospho-ITAM binding to SYK-tSH2. (A) Schematic overview of the TR-FRET-based assay. (B) Titration of TR-FRET signal from FITC-labelled FCER1G phospho-ITAM with unlabelled phosphorylated (blue dots) and non-phosphorylated (red squares) FCER1G ITAM peptides. $n=3$; error bars show SD.

Analogous TR-FRET assays were established to measure TYROBP, CD3G and CD79A phospho-ITAM binding to SYK-tSH2 (Fig. 7). For all assays, addition of competitor phospho-ITAM could titrate the FRET signal.

See **Additional information (section 4)** for TR-FRET assay conditions and methods.

Figure 7. Biochemical selectivity assay for phospho-ITAM binding to SYK-tSH2. Shown are titrations of TR-FRET signals from TYROBP (A), CD3G (B) and CD79A (C) FITC-conjugated phospho-ITAM peptides with unlabelled phosphorylated (blue dots) and non-phosphorylated (red squares) ITAM peptides. $n=3$; error bars show SD.

Biophysical assay

Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR)

We used SPR to measure the biophysical properties of FCER1G phospho-ITAM binding to SYK-tSH2. The phospho-ITAM binds with an equilibrium dissociation constant of 6.0 nM, with a very fast on rate, coupled with a relatively fast off rate (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Single-cycle kinetics of FCER1G phospho-ITAM binding to SYK-tSH2 by SPR. Biotinylated SYK-tSH2 was bound to a streptavidin sensor chip before flowing through unlabelled FCER1G phospho-ITAM peptide with increasing concentrations. Shown is the actual response (blue) together with the fitted response (red).

Differential Scanning Fluorimetry (DSF)

DSF, which measures protein unfolding, is an alternative quick screening method for binding of ligands to proteins. To determine if SYK-tSH2 is amenable to DSF analysis, we measured the melting temperature of SYK-tSH2 with and without the FCER1G phospho-ITAM. Addition of the phospho-ITAM stabilized SYK-tSH2, giving rise to a 5.9°C increase in melting temperature (Fig. 9). In conclusion, DSF is a suitable technique for screening ligand binding to SYK-tSH2.

Figure 9. DSF analysis of FCER1G phospho-ITAM binding to SYK-tSH2. Assay was performed with 2 μM protein and 10 μM peptide.

Isothermal Titration Calorimetry (ITC)

We used Isothermal Titration Calorimetry (ITC) with MicroCal Auto-iTC200 to measure the binding of the potential compounds and control FCER1G peptide with SYK protein. The fully automated MicroCal Auto-iTC200 provides a highly sensitive isothermal thermogram. It is possible to get a direct, label-free in solution measurement of all binding parameters in a single experiment. A trace of the control peptide binding experiment is shown as a thermogram in Figure 10. Where the receptor/ SYK was of 40uM in concentration and the ligands/compounds were 400 uM which was 10 times higher in concentration. The KD was obtained ~20.8 nM. Parameter N suggests 1.45 molecules of FCER1G control peptide bind to a one molecule of SYK. Considering the fact that SPR and ITC are two different experiments, the KD values obtained from each experiment are not very different from each other.

Figure 10. SYK ITC experiment: SYK protein with FCER1G peptide at 1:1 stoichiometric ratio.

See **Additional information (section 5-7)** for biophysical assay conditions and methods.

Screening

SYK-FCER1G Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI) TR-FRET assay for High-throughput Screening (HTS)

The TR-FRET assay for His-SYK and FITC-FCER1G peptides was miniaturized and optimized into a 1536-well format for uHTS. The TR-FRET uHTS assay was robust with $S/B > 10$ and $Z' > 0.6$ across 109 1536-well plates. The primary uHTS campaign was completed with a total of 138,214 compounds and produced 294 primary positive hits (% Control < 60) with a hit rate 0.2% (Fig. 11A). Dose-response confirmatory screens were completed for the 294 primary hits with cherry-picked library compounds and 112 re-ordered commercially available compounds. 43 compounds within various chemical clusters demonstrated $IC_{50} < 30 \mu M$ (Fig. 11B). Following solubility assessment in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) by nephelometer and secondary assays confirming protein-compound interaction including GST-pull down (Figure 12A), bio-layer interferometry (BLI) direct binding (Figure 12B), and thermal shift assay (TSA) (Figure 12C), two compounds were identified as

potential inhibitors (Fig. 11C) but subsequent literature searches identified that these compounds indiscriminately react with proteins (Karatas, Akbarzadeh et al. 2020).

Figure 11. SYK-FCER1G PPI TR-FRET assay for HTS. (A) Results of primary uHTS of 138,214 compounds, (B) Hits from dose-response confirmatory screen, (C) Two compounds assessed by secondary assays but later found to have low specificity.

Figure 12. Secondary assays for compounds AD-S-072 and AD-S-081 A) Western blot of dose response GST pull down from 3x dilution of cell lysate from HEK293 cells co-expressing full-length GST-SYK and FCER1g-vFlag treated with 6.25μM, 25μM, and 100μM AD-S-072 (top) or AD-S-081 (bottom) or DMSO control B) Bio-Layer Interferometry (BLI) for compound/protein direct binding for AD-S-072 (left, Kd: 8.4 μM) or AD-S-081 (right, Kd: 10.3 μM) C) Melting curves of full length SYK from the thermal shift assay (TSA) with the addition of AD-S-072 (left) or AD-S-081 (right), DMSO, a non-specific peptide, or a binding peptide as a positive control.

See **Additional information (section 8)** for screening conditions and methods.

CONCLUSION

SYK was selected as a target from genetics and RNAseq data, and FCER1G was nominated due to RNAseq data. This TEP focuses on the inhibition of the specific interaction of SYK-tSH2 and the p-ITAM sequence of FCER1G gene. Co-crystal structures of SYK-tSH2 with p-ITAM sequences from CD3E, FCER1G, CD3G, and TYROBP provide structural information to aid development of a selective inhibitor for FCER1G. Development of biochemical (TR-FRET) and biophysical (SPR, DSF, ITC) assays are critical to characterize inhibitors of the SYK-tSH2/FCER1G interaction. The tools that have been provided in this TEP provide a basis for a medicinal chemistry program to develop chemical probes to interrogate the potential roles of SYK and FCER1G in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

1. Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

SYKA-c020 tagged: Human SYK tandem SH2 domains (SYK-tSH2), M6-N269. Contains an N-terminal His6 and TEV cleavage site. Protein produced in bacterial cells. Used in activity assays.

Gene name	SYK
Uniprot ID	P43405
Region	M6-N269

Description	Tyrosine-protein kinase SYK. Tandem SH2 domains.
Synonyms	Spleen tyrosine kinase, p72-Syk
Construct ID	SYKA-c020
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	32327.60 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	34380
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMADSANHLPPFFGNITREEAEDYLVQGGMSDGLYLLRQ SRNYLGGFALSVAHGRKAHHYTIERELNGTYAIAGGRTHASPADLCHYHSQESDGLVCLLKK PFNRPQGVQPKTGFEDLKENLIREYVKQWTWNLQGGQALEQAIISQKPQLEKLIATTAHEKMP WFHKGISREESEQIVLIGSKTNGKFLIRARDNNGSYALCLLHEGKVLHYRIDKDKTKLSIPEG KKFDTLWQLVEHYSYKADGLLRVLTVPQKIGTQGNVN

Purified Protein

SEC: SYKA-c020 (with tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: SYKA-c020 (with tag)	
Observed Mass:	32328.7 Da
Protein yield:	31 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 5 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

SYKA-c020 cleaved: Human SYK tandem SH2 domains, M6-N269. Protein produced in bacterial cells. Used for crystallography.

Gene name	SYK
Uniprot ID	P43405
Region	M6-N269

Description	Tyrosine-protein kinase SYK. Tandem SH2 domains.
Synonyms	Spleen tyrosine kinase, p72-Syk
Construct ID	SYKA-c020

Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV, C-terminal AviTag
Protein mass (with tag)	32327.60 Da
Protein mass (without tag)	29861.95 Da
Extinction Coefficient without tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	32890
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMADSANHLPPFFGNITREEAEDYLVQGGMSDGLYLLRQSRNYLGGFALSVAHGRKAHHYTIERELNGTYAIAGGRTHASPADLCHYHSQESDGLVCLLKKPFNRPQGVQPKTGPFDLKENLIREYVKQTWNLQGGQALEQAIISQKPQLEKLIATTAHEKMPWFHGKISRESEQIVLIGSKTNGKFLIRARDNNGSYALCLLHEGKVLHYRIDKDKTGKLSIPEGKKFDTLWQLVEHYSYKADGLLRVLTVPQCQKIGTQGNVN
Protein sequence (with tag)	SMADSANHLPPFFGNITREEAEDYLVQGGMSDGLYLLRQSRNYLGGFALSVAHGRKAHHYTIERELNGTYAIAGGRTHASPADLCHYHSQESDGLVCLLKKPFNRPQGVQPKTGPFDLKENLIREYVKQTWNLQGGQALEQAIISQKPQLEKLIATTAHEKMPWFHGKISRESEQIVLIGSKTNGKFLIRARDNNGSYALCLLHEGKVLHYRIDKDKTGKLSIPEGKKFDTLWQLVEHYSYKADGLLRVLTVPQCQKIGTQGNVN

Purified Protein	
SEC: SYKA-c020 (without tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: SYKA-c020 (without tag)	
Observed Mass:	29863.1 Da

Protein yield:	25 mg/L of culture
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Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 7. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 8. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 9. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 10. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 8. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 9. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 10. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 11. Wash column with 5 ml W30. 12. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add His-tagged TEV protease to the protein at a 1:20 mass ratio and dialyse in 1-2 litres of SEC buffer at 4°C overnight.

TEV cleavage and reverse IMAC	2. Pass the protein solution through a 0.8 ml Ni-Sepharose column equilibrated with SEC buffer and collect the eluant. Wash the beads successively with 3 ml each of Lysis, W30, and Elution buffer. Determine the fractions containing the cleaved protein by SDS-PAGE and pool. The protein should be in the flowthrough, lysis, or W30 wash fractions, while the His-tag and TEV protease should be present only in the elution fraction.
Purification step 3: Size-exclusion chromatography	6. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 7. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 8. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 9. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 10. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N ₂ , and store at -80°C.

SYKA-c022 cleaved and biotinylated: Human SYK tandem SH2 domains, M6-N269. Protein produced in bacterial cells. Used in biophysical assays.

Gene name	SYK
Uniprot ID	P43405
Region	M6-N269

Description	Tyrosine-protein kinase SYK. Tandem SH2 domains.
Synonyms	Spleen tyrosine kinase, p72-Syk
Construct ID	SYKA-c022
Parental vector	pNIC-Bio3
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV, C-terminal AviTag
Protein mass (with tag)	34718.20 Da
Protein mass (with tag removed)	32252.50 Da + 226 Da biotin
Extinction Coefficient without tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	39880

Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMADSANHLPFFFGNITREEAEDYLVQGGMSDGLYLLRQSRNYLGGFALSVAHGRKAHHYTIERELNGTYAIAGGRTHASPADLCHYHSQESDGLVCLLKKPFNRPQGVQPKTGPFDLKENLIREYVKQWTWNLQGGQALEQAIISQKPQLEKLIATTAHEKMPWFHGKISREESEQIVLIGSKTNGKFLIRARDNNGSYALCLLHEGKVLHYRIDKDKTGKLSIPEGKKFDTLWQLVEHYSYKADGLLRVLTVPCCQKIGTQGNVNSSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE
Protein sequence (after tag removal)	SMADSANHLPFFFGNITREEAEDYLVQGGMSDGLYLLRQSRNYLGGFALSVAHGRKAHHYTIERELNGTYAIAGGRTHASPADLCHYHSQESDGLVCLLKKPFNRPQGVQPKTGPFDLKENLIREYVKQWTWNLQGGQALEQAIISQKPQLEKLIATTAHEKMPWFHGKISREESEQIVLIGSKTNGKFLIRARDNNGSYALCLLHEGKVLHYRIDKDKTGKLSIPEGKKFDTLWQLVEHYSYKADGLLRVLTVPCCQKIGTQGNVNSSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE

Purified Protein	
SEC: SYKA-c022 (tag removed, biotinylated)	<p>The SEC chromatogram shows a single peak at approximately 85 mL with a maximum absorbance of about 1000 mAU. The Western blot shows a single band at approximately 35 kDa, with molecular weight markers at 150, 100, 75, 50, 37, 25, 20, and 15 kDa.</p>
Intact Mass Deconvolution: SYKA-c022 (tag removed, biotinylated)	<p>+ESI Scan (rt 0.967-1.182 min, 14 scans) Frag=250.0V SYKA_c022.d Deconvoluted (Isotope Width=11.0)</p> <p>Major peak at 32479.85 Da. Other labeled peaks at 41492.51 and 49978.50 Da.</p>
Observed Mass:	32479.9 Da
Protein yield:	13.3 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE-pBirA
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan) and 50 µg/ml streptomycin (Strep). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).

Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain <i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE-pBirA, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml), cm (34 µg/ml), and strep (50 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. At the same time, add 30 ml of 10 mM biotin dissolved in 10 mM bicine (pH 8.3). Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 12. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 13. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 14. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 15. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 13. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 14. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 15. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 16. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 17. Wash column with 5 ml W30. 18. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: TEV cleavage and reverse IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add His-tagged TEV protease to the protein at a 1:20 mass ratio and dialyse in 1-2 litres of SEC buffer at 4°C overnight. 2. Pass the protein solution through a 0.8 ml Ni-Sepharose column equilibrated with SEC buffer and collect the eluant. Wash the beads successively with 10 ml each of Lysis, W30, and Elution buffer. Determine the fractions containing the cleaved protein by SDS-PAGE and pool. The protein should be in the flowthrough, Lysis, or W30 fractions, while the His-tag and TEV protease should be present only in the elution fraction.
Purification step 3: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 12. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min.

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| | <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 13. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 14. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 15. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C. |
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2. Peptides

FCER1G-phospho-ITAM(62-81): DGV(pY)TGLSTRNQET(pY)ETLKH, dissolved to 10 mM in water.

FCER1G-phospho-ITAM(62-81)-FITC: DGV(pY)TGLSTRNQET(pY)ETLKHK-FITC, dissolved to 1.9 mM in 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5)

FCER1G-nonphospho-ITAM(62-81): DGVYTGLSTRNQETYETLKHK, dissolved to 3 mM in 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.5)

TYROBP-phospho-ITAM(88-107): ESP(pY)QELQGQRSDV(pY)SDLNT, dissolved to 10 mM in water

TYROBP-phospho-ITAM(88-107)-FITC: ESP(pY)QELQGQRSDV(pY)SDLNTK-FITC, dissolved to 2 mM in 50 mM HEPES, pH 7.5

TYROBP-nonphospho-ITAM(88-107): ESPYQELQGQRSDVYSDLNT, dissolved to 3 mM in 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5)

CD3G-phospho-ITAM(157-176): DQL(pY)QPLKDREDDQ(pY)SHLQG, dissolved to 10 mM in water

CD3G-phospho-ITAM(157-176)-FITC: DQL(pY)QPLKDREDDQ(pY)SHLQGK-FITC, dissolved to 2 mM in 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5)

CD3G-nonphospho-ITAM(157-176): DQLYQPLKDREDDQYSHLQG, dissolved to 3 mM in 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5)

CD3G-phospho-ITAM(157-176): DQL(pY)QPLKDREDDQ(pY)SHLQG, dissolved to 10 mM in water

CD3G-phospho-ITAM(157-176)-FITC: DQL(pY)QPLKDREDDQ(pY)SHLQGK-FITC, dissolved to 2 mM in 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5)

CD3G-nonphospho-ITAM(157-176): DQLYQPLKDREDDQYSHLQG, dissolved to 3 mM in 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5)

3. Crystallography and data collection

Prior to crystallography, SYK-tSH2 (SYKA-c020) protein, with 6His tag removed, was buffer exchanged into 10 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM TCEP and diluted to 12 mg/ml. Crystals with phospho-ITAM peptides were obtained by incubating protein with peptide in a 1:1.1 ratio for 30 min on ice before setting up crystal drops. Apo SYK-tSH2 crystals were obtained from mixing protein and precipitant in a 1:1 ratio of 200 mM potassium thiocyanate, 15% glycerol and 26% PEG3350. Rectangular prisms are observed after 1 week at 20°C. FCER1G phospho-ITAM(62-81) bound SYK-tSH2 was obtained from mixing protein with peptide and precipitant in a 1:2 ratio of 30 mM sodium nitrate, 30 mM dibasic sodium phosphate, 30 mM ammonium sulphate, 100 mM Tris/BICINE pH 8.5, 10% PEG 20000 and 20% PEG 500 MME. Rectangular prisms were obtained after one week at 20°C. TYROBP phospho-ITAM(88-107) bound SYK-tSH2 was obtained from mixing protein with peptide and precipitant in a 2:1 ratio of 30 mM sodium nitrate, 30 mM dibasic sodium phosphate, 30 mM ammonium sulphate, 100 mM Tris/BICINE pH 8.5, 10% PEG 20000 and 20% PEG 500 MME. Rectangular prisms were obtained after two weeks at 20°C. CD3G phospho-ITAM(157-176) bound SYK-tSH2 was obtained from mixing protein with peptide and precipitant in a 2:1 ratio of 20 mM DL-malic acid, 40 mM MES, 40 mM Tris (pH 8.0) and 30% PEG 1000. Irregular-shaped crystals were obtained after 4 days at 20°C. Crystals were loop-mounted and transferred to a cryosolution containing well solution. All

diffraction data were collected at Diamond Light Source. Data were processed using DIALS (doi:10.1107/s2059798317017235) and structures were solved by molecular replacement using the program PHASER (doi:10.1107/s0907444906045975).

4. TR-FRET assay development

TR-FRET experiments were performed in 20 μ l reactions, using 384-well shallow-well microplates (PerkinElmer). All reagents were diluted in assay buffer containing 25 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 0.1% BSA and 0.05% Tween-20. See Table 1 for protein and peptide concentrations used. After dispensing 6His-SYK-tSH2 protein (5 μ l at 4x concentration) to the well, a dilution series of competitor peptide (5 μ l at 4x concentration) was added. The mixture was incubated for 30 min (at RT). FITC-labelled peptide was added (5 μ l at 4x concentration) and the mixture was incubated for a further 30 min (at RT). Finally, Tb-conjugated anti-6His antibody (MAb Anti 6His Tb cryptate Gold; Cisbio) was added to the reaction (5 μ l at 4x concentration; 50 ng/ml final). After a 2h incubation (at RT), TR-FRET signals were measured on a PheraStar FSX (BGM) using a Lanthascreen Optics Module. A 200 μ s delay was used after excitation with a flash lamp before measurement of fluorescence emission at 490 and 520 nm. TR-FRET ratios of 490 to 520 nm were calculated.

Phospho-ITAM	Peptide Conc.	SYK-tSH2 Conc.
FCER1G	8 nM	4 nM
TYROBP	8 nM	16 nM
CD3G	8 nM	4 nM
CD79	32 nM	8 nM

Table 1. Concentrations of FITC-phospho ITAM peptides and 6His-SYK-tSH2 proteins used in TR-FRET assays

5. Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR)

Binding experiments were performed using a Biacore S200 instrument (Cytiva) and a SA sensor chip in a buffer consisting of 10 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 150 mM NaCl, 0.5 mM TCEP and 1% DMSO. Biotinylated SYK-tSH2 was immobilized to the chip, giving 4000 RU. Single cycle kinetic analysis was performed by injecting FCER1G phospho-ITAM peptide at increasing concentrations (3.9, 7.8, 16, 31, 62, 125, 250, 500, and 1,000 nM) for 120 s, and equilibrium analysis was performed with a 650 sec association and 1,200 sec dissociation phase. Data was fitted with Biacore S200 evaluation software, using a 1:1 binding model.

6. Differential Scanning Fluorimetry (DSF)/ Thermal Shift Assay (TSA)

SYK-tSH2 protein was diluted in assay buffer (2 μ M in 10 mM HEPES, 150 mM NaCl) containing Sypro Orange (1 in 1000 dilution (ThermoFisher) and incubated on ice for 30 min. FCER1G phospho-ITAM (500 μ M in DMSO) or DMSO alone was added to SYK-tSH2 to 2% of final volume and the mixture was incubated for a further 30 min on ice. Melting curves were obtained on an Mx3005p qPCR machine (Agilent), ramping up from 25 to 95 $^{\circ}$ C, at 1 $^{\circ}$ C min $^{-1}$. The data was fitted to the Boltzmann equation. The T_m was calculated by determining the maximum value of the first derivative of fluorescence transition.

To establish T_m of SYK in the presence or absence of compound or control, full-length SYK (2 μ M, purified as described above) and compound, control peptide (FCER1g-phospho-ITAM 62-81 peptide (GenScript, 1 μ M),

and FCER1g-nonphospho-ITAM 62-81 peptide (GenScript, 1 μ M)), or DMSO were mixed with 4X SYPRO Orange protein gel stain (Invitrogen S6650) and incubated at 25° C for 10 minutes. A gradient curve was established from 25° C to 80° C over the course of 30 minutes, ending with an 80° C hold for 15 seconds. Data were analyzed by GraphPad Prism.

7. Isothermal Titration Calorimetry (ITC)

SYK protein solution of 365 μ L was placed in the reaction cell. The ligand/compounds solution of 165 μ L was placed in the injection syringe. The ligand/compound concentration was 10 times higher than the concentration of SYK. Both ligand/compounds and SYK protein were in identical buffers [50mM HEPES (7.5), 200mM NaCl]. ITC experiments with compounds included 4% DMSO. Data was collected after an overnight experiment.

8. SYK-FCER1G PPI TR-FRET assay for HTS

uHTS reaction: SYK protein: 2 nM, FITC-p-FCER1G: 6 nM, and anti-His-Tb: 1:1000. Volume: 5 μ l per well. Background control: FITC-p-FCER1G: 6 nM and anti-His-Tb: 1:1000. Volume: 5 μ l per well.

9. GST pulldown

The dose response confirmatory GST pulldown with compounds AD-S-072 and AD-S-081 was performed using the following reagents: Glutathione Sepharose 4B (17075605, Cytiva); GST WB primary antibody: GST-Taq (2.6H1) Mouse mAb, 2624S, Cell Signaling, 1:1000 dilution; GST WB secondary antibody: peroxidase-conjugated AffiniPure Goat Anti-Mouse IgG (H+L), 115-035-003, Jackson Immuno Research, 1:5000 dilution; vFlag WB antibody: Monoclonal ANTI-FLAG M2-HRP antibody, A8592-1MG, Sigma, 1:1000 dilution. GST pulldown was performed as described (Yang, Fan et al. 2021).

10. Bio-Layer Interferometry

Bio-Layer Interferometry (BLI) for compound/protein direct binding was performed using the Octet RED384 system (Sartorius BioAnalytical Instruments) and biotinylated SYK-tSH2 protein (as previously described). The biotinylated SYK-tSH2 (50 μ g/mL) was loaded onto super streptavidin sensors in 50 μ L loading buffer (PBS + 0.02% Tween-20) for 10 minutes resulting in a 14 nm loading density. The assay was performed as described in (Li, Gera et al. 2021).

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